

FACULTY OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING

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**A WEB-BASED SOLUTION FOR FEDERATED
LEARNING WITH LLM-BASED AUTOMATION**

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ABSTRACT

Federated Learning (FL) presents a promising paradigm for collaborative machine learning across distributed devices. However, its implementation is hindered by the complexity of building reliable communication architectures and the requisite expertise in both machine learning and network programming. This thesis addresses this challenge by introducing a comprehensive solution that facilitates the seamless orchestration of FL tasks while integrating intent-based automation.

In the initial phase, we develop a user-friendly web application supporting the FedAvg algorithm, enabling users to easily configure parameters through an intuitive interface. The backend solution manages communication tasks between the parameter server and edge nodes, incorporating an efficient communication architecture. Additionally, we delve into implementing secondary functionalities like model compression and scheduling algorithms to optimize FL operations.

Building upon this foundation, we explore the frontier of intent-based automation in FL. Leveraging a fine-tuned Language Model (LLM) trained on a tailored dataset, our solution conducts FL tasks in response to high-level prompts provided by users increasing the accessibility of the provided solution.

Through this thesis, we contribute a practical framework for bridging the conceptualization and implementation of FL solutions. By providing a user-friendly interface, efficient communication, and automated task execution, our solution empowers researchers and practitioners to harness the potential of federated learning effectively.

Keywords: Federated learning, Distributed computing, Web sockets communication, Large language models, Transformer architecture, Intent-based automation.

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FOREWORD

This thesis focuses on developing a novel framework for orchestrating federated learning tasks and integrating a large language model for intent-based automation. This work was supported in part by the European Commission through the DESIRE6G (G.A. 101096466). The work is carried out as part of my MSc in Computer Science and Engineering. The work is carried out during my employment as a research assistant at Intelligent Connectivity and Networks/Systems Group (ICON) at the Center for Wireless Communications (CWC) of the University of Oulu, Finland.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

ML	Machine learning
DL	Deep learning
FL	Federated learning
PS	Parameter server
API	Application programming interface
AI	Artificial intelligence
LLM	Large Language model
GPT	Generative pre-trained transformer
NLP	Natural language processing
RNN	Recurrent neural network
GB	Gigabytes
VRAM	Virtual Random access memory
PEFT	Parameter efficient fine tuning
LoRA	Low rank adaptation
GPU	Graphical processing unit
QLoRA	Quantized low rank adaptation
NF4	4-bit normal float
CPU	Central processing unit
RAM	Random access memory
JSON	Javascript object notation
TCP	Transmission control protocol
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
SGD	Stochastic gradient descent
Adam	Adaptive Moment Estimation
AdaGrad	Adaptive Gradient Algorithm
RMSProp	root mean squared propagation
Adamw	Adaptive Moment Estimation with weight decay
REST	Representational State Transfer
CNN	Convolutional neural network
$f(w)$	Federated learning objective function
$F_k(w)$	local objective function
n_k	number of data points for client k
n	total number of data points
$\mathcal{P}_k$	set of datapoints in client k
$ \cdot $	absolute value
w	weight parameters
$\mathbb{R}^d$	d dimensional euclidean space
k	client number
K	total number of clients
$\sum$	summation expression
η	learning rate
w_0	initial weights
m	number of active clients in a communication round

S_t	list of m active clients
w_{t+1}^k	weight update for client k in $t + 1$ th communication round.
m_t	total number of data points for active clients in communication round t
w_{t+1}	global model weights for communication round $t + 1$
$\mathcal{B}$	client data separated into batches
b	individual batch
Δl	calculated gradient loss
x	floating point value
α	lower threshold of floating point value
β	upper threshold for floating point value
x_q	quantized integer value
α_q	lower threshold for quantized integer
β_q	upper threshold for quantized integer
S	scaling factor
Z	zero point value
f_q	quantization function
f_d	dequantization function
pos	absolute position of the token in a sequence
d_{model}	dimension of embedding vector
Q	query vector
K	key vector
V	value vector
d_k	dimension of key and query vectors
d_v	dimension of value vector
W_i^Q	parameter matrix for query
W_i^K	parameter matrix for key
W_i^V	parameter matrix for value
W_i^O	parameter matrix for output
h	number of parallel attention heads
W	weight matrix of the LLM
B	low rank adapted matrix of W
A	low rank adapted matrix of W
ΔW	gradient of weights of the LLM
$\hat{w}_n$	compressed weights of the FL client

1. INTRODUCTION

A novel web-based application with inbuilt communication architecture to perform federated learning (FL) tasks without relying on programming proficiency will be outlined in this thesis. This chapter initiates the discussion by giving some intuition on the subject and the motivation behind the tasks carried out during the thesis. Our contribution and outline of the thesis will be discussed later.

1.1. Background and Motivation

With the recent developments in machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), a surge in organizations adopting ML and DL in their business solutions can be observed. This can be attributed to the fact that there is an abundance of user-generated data to feed into these ML systems. In the conventional machine learning approach, model training occurs in a centralized server where raw user data are communicated to the server for model training. This poses a threat to user privacy since private data has to be shared with a separate party. To alleviate this threat, FL [1] has emerged as a novel paradigm that enables decentralized training of models enabling data privacy preservation.

FL which stems from research on distributed optimization and privacy-preserving ML, is a form of collaborative learning where rather than communicating raw data from the users, the model is trained by communicating model weights among edge nodes and a parameter server (PS), minimizing the risk of exploitation of private user data. After the inception of FL by Google [1], it has been adopted in diverse contexts across various domains such as global COVID diagnosis [2], vehicular networks [2], wireless communications [3, 4].

Researchers and other stakeholders participating in FL implementations must rely on programming expertise and develop a seamless communication architecture between edge nodes and the PS. The FL community mostly relies on some common frameworks such as Flower [5], PySyft [6], TensorFlow Federated [7], and p [8]. Complex systems for FL can be developed using these frameworks with both programming and FL domain expertise. Although deep knowledge about Application programming interface (API) provided by some of the frameworks might be required for adopting to a use case. Also, these solutions might not be user-friendly for researchers with minimal expertise in FL. This lack of accessibility can hinder broader adoption and experimentation on FL tasks.

Moreover, with the recent disruption in the Artificial intelligence (AI) community with Large language models (LLM), numerous fields have opted to adopt LLM technologies in the automation of complex tasks such as data analysis [9], code generation [10, 11], robotics [12, 13] and communication technologies [14, 15]. As evident from some of these solutions, LLMs have become an enabler in producing high-level intent-based applications.

Due to these developments, there is a growing potential for simplifying and automating the FL process, to make it more accessible to a broader range of users. This sets the stage for our proposed solution, which aims to bridge the gap between

conceptualizing and implementing FL solutions through an innovative web-based and an LLM-based automated solution.

1.2. Contribution

One of the major challenges in engaging in FL tasks using multiple hardware entities as edge nodes and PS is a reliable communication architecture has to be built from scratch for the devices to communicate. Consequently, ML expertise along with general programming experience in the realm of network programming in particular is required. Our goal is to bridge the gap between conceptualizing a FL solution and implementing it. Accordingly, we introduce a web-based solution with an inbuilt communication architecture to easily orchestrate FL tasks. Furthermore, we explore the possibility of integrating an intent-based platform where using a fine-tuned LLM, FL operations are carried out according to the user prompt provided. In summary, our contribution is as follows,

- In the initial stage, a standard web application to support the FedAvg [1] algorithm, is developed to perform FL tasks easily. Users will be able to select parameters required for running the algorithm through a provided web interface while communication tasks between the PS and the edge nodes will be handled by the provided back-end solution. An efficient communication architecture to communicate between the PS and edge nodes is investigated.
- Moreover, the implementation of secondary functionalities in FL such as model compression to optimize the transmission of model weights and scheduling algorithms to schedule clients participating in the FL task is explored.
- Subsequently, as a step towards automating FL, intent-based automation of the developed solution is explored where FL tasks are carried out according to a provided high-level prompt. For this purpose, an open-source LLM is fine-tuned on a new dataset tailored towards the intended purpose.

1.3. Thesis Outline

The remaining of the thesis is organized as follows,

- Chapter 2 - summarizes the literature review done for the thesis work.
- Chapter 3 - delves into the details of system design and methodology followed for implementing the web application including FedAvg, implementing secondary functionalities around FL, and LLM integration to aid the automation of FL. The methodology followed for fine-tuning the LLM model is also discussed in this chapter.
- Chapter 4 - presents experimental results obtained through simulations done using the standard web application and the LLM integrated application. Additionally, a comprehensive evaluation of the fine-tuned LLM model is provided in the chapter.

- Chapter 5 - A conclusion about all the work carried out during the thesis process is given in this chapter.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Federated Learning

FL is a paradigm of ML where models are trained collaboratively using multiple edge nodes (referred to as clients here onwards), and a PS. The PS is responsible for orchestrating the model training. In contrast to traditional ML training, data across clients are not communicated to a PS for optimization, rather the model optimization occurs locally in the participating clients. Hence, the client's private data is not compromised in the FL setting.

Figure 1. Centralized Machine Learning vs Federated Learning

The distinction becomes evident when examining Figure 1. In the centralized ML setting, participating clients are required to upload their personal data to a centralized server for model training. Conversely, in the FL setting locally trained model weights are transmitted to the central server, which functions as the PS. Here, the PS aggregates the model weights to update the global model which is then distributed to participating clients for the next iteration of training.

The objective of FL can be formulated as follows [1],

$$\min_{w \in \mathbb{R}^d} f(w) = \sum_{k=1}^K \frac{n_k}{n} F_k(w), \quad (1)$$

where $F_k(w)$ is the local objective function for the client k . It is assumed here that the total dataset is partitioned among K number of clients. Furthermore $n_k = |\mathcal{P}_k|$ where $\mathcal{P}_k$ is the set of data points assigned for the k^{th} client.

For a typical ML problem, the local objective can be formulated as follows,

$$F_k(w) = \frac{1}{n_k} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{P}_k} f_i(w), \quad (2)$$

where $f_i(w) = \ell(x_i, y_i; w)$ is the loss value on prediction made for datapoint (x_i, y_i) using the model weights w .

With these objectives in mind, *FederatedAveraging* or *FedAvg* has been introduced in [1], and is summarized in the algorithm 1. The hyperparameters used in FedAvg algorithm are,

- Client fraction(C) which controls the fraction of clients in the pool of all the clients participating in training in a single communication round.
- Number of local epochs (E) represents how many local iterations through the dataset of each client will be done.
- Local minibatch size (B) defines the size of the individual batches taken during the local training process.

Algorithm 1. FedAvg Algorithm.

Inputs : K - number of clients, η - learning rate, C - Client fraction, E - Number of local epochs, B - local minibatch size

Server Executes :

```

initialize  $w_0$ 
for each round  $t = 1, 2, \dots$  do
   $m \leftarrow \max(C \cdot K, 1)$ 
   $S_t \leftarrow$  (random set of  $m$  clients)
  for each client  $k \in S_t$  in parallel do
     $w_{t+1}^k \leftarrow \text{ClientUpdate}(k, w_t)$ 
  end
   $m_t \leftarrow \sum_{k \in S_t} n_k$ 
   $w_{t+1} \leftarrow \sum_{k \in S_t} \frac{n_k}{m_t} w_{t+1}^k$ 
end

```

Client Update(k, w): Update run on client k

```

 $\mathcal{B} \leftarrow$  (split  $\mathcal{P}_k$  into batches of size  $B$ )
for each local epoch  $i$  from 1 to  $E$  do
  for batch  $b \in \mathcal{B}$  do
     $w \leftarrow w - \eta \Delta l(w; b)$ 
  end
end
return  $w$  to server.

```

2.2. Model Compression

One of the major challenges in FL is scalability. As the model size and the number of clients grow, encountering a communication bottleneck within the FL framework may become inevitable. To alleviate that, model compression schemes have been adopted in the FL literature.

2.2.1. Quantization

Quantization is a technique for making models compact by reducing the precision of tensors. For example, a 32-bit precision of *float32* is reduced to a lower precision such as an 8-bit precision of *int8*. With regard to that, a mapping,

$$x \in [\alpha, \beta] \rightarrow x_q \in [\alpha_q, \beta_q], \quad (3)$$

needs to be realized where x and x_q are floating point and quantized integer values respectively. In that aspect, a quantization function [16] is formulated using *affine mapping* between floating point value and the quantized integer, and using *clip* function as follows.

$$f_q(x, S, Z) = \text{clip}(\text{round}(\frac{x}{S} + Z), \alpha_q, \beta_q), \quad (4)$$

where the clip function is defined as,

$$\text{clip}(x, \alpha, \beta) = \begin{cases} \alpha & \text{if } x < \alpha, \\ x & \text{if } \alpha \leq x \leq \beta, \\ \beta & \text{if } x > \beta. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Here, S and Z are quantization parameters, where S is an arbitrary positive real number and Z maps to the 0 in floating value to the corresponding value in quantized data type.

The recovery of the floating point value through de-quantization can be done using the following equation.

$$f_d(x_q, S, Z) = S(x_q - Z). \quad (6)$$

Usually in the application of quantization in the FL setting, locally trained models are quantized and communicated to the PS, where de-quantization is done to recover the original model weights before doing the model aggregation.

2.2.2. Sparsification

Sparsification [17] is another method for compressing models within the FL framework. This technique involves the selective retention of only a subset of gradients through sparse selection. *Top-k* and *Rand-k* are the most widely used sparsification methods.

- In the *Top-k* method, top k percent of gradients with the highest absolute values are selected while other values are set to zero
- In the *Rand-k* method, k percent of gradients are selected based on a random permutation of the list of gradients

In the FL setting, only the sparse selection of k percent of gradients and their values are communicated by the client to the PS, making communication more efficient.

2.3. Existing FL Frameworks

One major problem with FL is the complexity of transforming from a concept to a solution. Most of the time ideas are implemented using a single computer where a program is created to simulate an FL setting. However in this setting, although we can evaluate the theoretical aspects of the FL, practical aspects such as latency, the bandwidth required for transmission, and other bottlenecks in communicating model weights cannot be evaluated since real communication between clients and PS is not occurring.

There are several solutions both open source and commercial where implementation of FL solution is made easy. Flower [5], PySyft [6], TensorFlow Federated [7], and p [8] are some of the commonly used open-source frameworks to implement FL. One common trait of all these solutions is, that they provide APIs where the end user has to program the solution. The drawback is that one must know how to program and these APIs must be learned to implement an FL solution which adds an overhead in time to get from concept to solution.

Some commercial solutions for simplifying FL tasks exist where the implementation is done using a web application. FedML [18], Acuratio [19], and Apheris [20] are some of the solutions that have been operating in the realm of FL to simplify FL tasks using a web application. However, a major caveat in these solutions is that although they are web-based, the core FL algorithm must be written from scratch. Sometimes only the communication infrastructure is provided where the particular FL algorithm needs to be uploaded as a file or a zipped file according to a pre-determined code structure compatible with the solution. Hence, our work aims to implement a no-code platform where everything can be orchestrated from the web application except the neural network architecture that needs to be uploaded as a file.

2.4. Large Language Models

In recent years, LLMs have revolutionized the AI community, through their remarkable capacity in understanding and generating human-like texts through various domains of tasks. Notably, generative pre-trained transformers (GPT) [21, 22] in particular have made great progress in the Natural Language Processing (NLP) paradigm. LLMs have been utilized in many tasks such as machine translation, question-answering systems, and programming tasks and emergent abilities have been explored in tasks like reasoning and decision-making. This spectacular performance of LLMs can be attributed to the large number of model parameters trained on a huge text corpus typically extracted from the web.

The success of LLMs has been further accelerated by large corporations open-sourcing their pre-trained language models for use by the general public. *Llama* [23] and *Llama2* [24] which spans models with 7B to 70B parameters released by *Meta AI*, and *Mistral 7B* [25], *Mistral 8x7B* [26] by *Mistral.ai* with parameters ranging from 7B to 13B are some of the widely used open-source LLMs in the community.

Every LLM mentioned here occupies some variation of the transformer architecture depicted in Figure 2, originally defined in [27], where the transformer is made up of two blocks, encoder (shown on the left) and decoder (shown on the right). A stack of

$N = 6$ layers of both encoder and decoder are used. The next subsection discusses the original transformer architecture defined by the aforementioned paper.

2.4.1. Transformer Architecture

The text corpus used in training the language model initially undergoes a pre-processing step called tokenization [28], where the words in the natural language are decomposed into smaller parts called tokens. These tokens usually take the form of words, characters, or sub-words based on the employed tokenization strategy. These tokens act as the input to both the encoder and decoder. Generally, the goal of auto-regressive models such as GPT-3 is to predict the next token, given an input sequence of tokens.

Figure 2. Transformer architecture.(encoder on left and decoder on right block) ¹.

Embedding Vectors

For the encoding process, the input tokens are converted into a vector where each token is assigned a numerical value according to an embedding algorithm employed. This word embedding vector acts as the input to the first encoder layer while for subsequent encoder layers, output from the previous encoder layer acts as the input embedding vector. All the embedding vectors take the size $d_{model} = 512$.

Positional Encoding

In the pre-transformer era, Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) served as the dominant architecture for NLP tasks. RNNs were favored due to their inherent recurrence nature, which provided access to information regarding the position of specific tokens within a sequence. However, with regard to transformers, positional knowledge needs to be induced since positional knowledge does not exist inherently. In [27], this is done by adding a vector of the same size d_{model} to the embedding vector, where the vector for positional encoding is induced with knowledge about the position using sine and cosine functions as follows,

$$PE_{(pos,2i)} = \sin\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d_{model}}}\right). \quad (7)$$

$$PE_{(pos,2i+1)} = \cos\left(\frac{pos}{10000^{2i/d_{model}}}\right). \quad (8)$$

Here, pos represents the absolute position of the token in a sequence of tokens while $i \in [0, d_{model}/2]$ represents the corresponding dimension related to the embedding vector.

Multi-Head Attention

As seen from Figure 2, the positional encoded vector is next passed through the multi-head attention layer, which is the first sub-layer of the encoder. The multi-head attention layer is equipped with an underlying self-attention mechanism encompassed with parallelized scaled dot-product attention as seen from Figure 3

The power of associating contextual information in a sentence comes from the underlying self-attention mechanism. For example, in the sentence, "The dog didn't fetch the ball because it was too sleepy", the self-attention mechanism helps in understanding that it refers to the dog in this sentence, thus helping in understanding contextual information.

Scaled dot-product attention is the mechanism that enables this which is powered by the attention function given by,

$$Attention(Q, K, V) = softmax\left(\frac{QK^T}{\sqrt{d_k}}\right)V \quad (9)$$

¹Transformer model architecture originally appeared in [27] with granted permission to reproduce figures for scholarly works.

³Attention mechanism figures originally appeared in [27] with granted permission to reproduce figures for scholarly works.

Figure 3. Attention mechanism, scaled dot-product attention (shown on the left) and multi-head attention (shown on the right) ³

Here Q is the Query vector and K is the Key vector with dimensions d_k , and V is the Value vector with dimension d_v acting as the input to the attention function. The term $\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ is used for scaling purposes. However, in practice, matrices are used for efficiency. It is evident that 9 is synonymous with the left side on Figure 3, where matrix multiplication of Q, K is scaled with $\frac{1}{\sqrt{d_k}}$ followed by *Softmax* and further multiplied by V .

The key takeaway from [27] is the multi-head attention, where rather than using a single attention layer, the attention mechanism is run h times in parallel, improving the model's performance by enabling the model to focus on various positions and providing multiple representation sub-spaces.

As illustrated in the right side of Figure 3, independently run attention layers are concatenated to produce output by multi-head attention as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} MultiHead(Q, K, V) &= Concat(head_1, \dots, head_h)W^O, \\ \text{where } head_i &= Attention(QW_i^Q, KW_i^K, VW_i^V). \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Here, $W_i^Q \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{model} \times d_k}$, $W_i^K \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{model} \times d_k}$ and $W_i^V \in \mathbb{R}^{d_{model} \times d_v}$ are learnable parameters which is used to create linear projections of input Q, K and V matrices, and d_{model} is the output dimension of each sub-layer and the embedding layer. In [27] the values of the parameters are given as follows: $d_{model} = 512$, $d_k, d_v = 64$ and $h = 8$.

Encoder and Decoder

A transformer architecture can be built mainly using both encoder and decoder (refer Figure 2) or using either encoder or decoder.

- **Encoder-only** models [29] are usually used in tasks where encoded representation of text can be utilized, such as text summarizing, named entity recognition, text classification, etc.
- **Decoder-only** models [21] are used in generative tasks such as auto-regressive models in text generation such as GPT models.
- **Encoder-Decoder** models [27] are used in generative tasks requiring encoded input representation, such as machine translation.

The encoder block usually consists of two sub-layers, the multi-head attention layer and the feed-forward layer. A residual connection [30] is made around each sub-layer to avoid vanishing gradient effects, where the output from the main function is summed to the input through residual connection, and layer normalization [31] is applied to the result. The summarized operation of each sub-layer can be denoted as,

$$output = LayerNorm(x + Function(x)) \quad (11)$$

where, x and $output$ represent the input and output of any sub-layer respectively, while $Function$ can be either multi-head attention or feed-forward network function.

Decoder blocks are almost similar to encoder blocks, except in encoder-decoder models two multi-head attention sub-layers are utilized where the first sub-layer is a masked multi-head attention. The masked multi-head attention ensures that during training, future tokens are masked, enabling the attention mechanism to solely consider preceding tokens up to the current position in the token sequence, which is crucial for the decoder's task of the next token generation.

In encoder-decoder models, the output from the encoder block serves as the Query (Q) and Key (K) input matrices for the second multi-head sub-layer. In contrast, the input Value (V) is derived from the output of the previous masked multi-head attention layer. However, a second sub-layer is not included in decoder-only models as there is no connection to an encoder.

The stacked decoder layers are followed by a linear fully connected layer and a softmax function to predict the probabilities corresponding to the next token. The output of the N stacks of decoder blocks is d_{model} in dimension. The linear layer projects this output into a vector of size d_{vocab} , and passes through softmax to predict probabilities corresponding to each value in the vector. Here, d_{vocab} is, the total number of tokens known by the model during training, hence the output from softmax reflects the likelihood of each token as the next in the sequence.

2.4.2. Parameter Efficient Fine-Tuning of LLM

Initially, LLMs are trained on large text corpus which possesses general knowledge. Hence, when adopting an LLM for downstream tasks, fine-tuning the model with a

tailored dataset specific to the task at hand may be necessary. Fine-tuning dataset usually comes in the form $\{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ where x_i is the input to the model and y_i is the target output from the model. Both x_i and y_i are in the form of a sequence of words or tokens.

However, fine-tuning an LLM fully with all the parameters included is a huge computationally expensive task requiring large Gigabytes (GB) of virtual random access memory (VRAM). Therefore, parameter-efficient fine-tuning (PEFT) methods have been explored in the literature.

Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) Fine-tuning

LoRA [32] is a widely used method for performing efficient fine-tuning on LLMs allegedly reducing trainable parameters by 10000 folds while lowering the graphical processing unit (GPU) memory requirement by 3 times compared to fully fine-tuning a GPT-3 175B parameter model with Adam optimizer.

During a full parameter fine-tune, forward and backward pass happens through all the weight parameters. However, in LoRA, pre-trained weights are frozen for weight updates, and re-parameterization of original weights is done through lower-rank decomposition of weight matrices. During the training process only these adapted weight matrices are updated through back-propagation as seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Low-Rank Adaptation (LoRA) Fine-Tuning

Consider any pre-trained weight matrix $W \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times k}$ in the model. In a full fine-tuning process, the gradient update can be denoted as $W + \Delta W$, where W is updated accordingly. In LoRA, W is kept frozen and ΔW is decomposed using lower rank matrices such that $\Delta W = BA$ with $\text{rank } r \ll \min(d, k)$, $A \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times k}$ is initialized randomly using a Gaussian distribution and $B \in \mathbb{R}^{d \times r}$ is initialized as zero in the beginning. Thus we can write,

$$W + \Delta W = W + BA \quad (12)$$

and the forward pass is calculated as,

$$h = Wx + \Delta Wx = Wx + BAx \quad (13)$$

For multi-head attention, we can assume $W \in \{W^q, W^k, W^v, W^o\}$ are learnable matrices referred earlier, h could be either Q, K, V or output from the attention when W^o is considered, and x can be either input embedding or intermediate hidden features produced by the neural network. Since significantly lower rank matrices are utilized for training, the number of training parameters is reduced significantly making the training procedure more efficient.

Once the fine-tuning is done, inference for the downstream tasks is done by merging the weights as follows,

$$W \leftarrow W + BA \quad (14)$$

By this means, adapting LoRA for multiple downstream tasks is possible since it is possible to train different LoRA adapters and plug them into the original model as above.

Quantized LoRA (QLoRA) Fine-tuning

QLoRA [33] is a variant of LoRA to enhance further the efficiency of fine-tuning a LLM. This is achieved by utilizing a quantized version of the transformer model, double quantization, and using paged optimizers.

Usually language model consists of tensors with either 32-bit or 16-bit precision floating points. In QLoRA, the transformer model is initially quantized to 4-bit precision where the tensors are converted to a data type called 4-bit normal float (NF4). NF4 is a novel quantization data type that produces theoretically optimal quantized results for normally distributed data. Additionally, QLoRA goes on to double quantization where quantization parameters are too quantized to reduce memory further. This quantized model follows LoRA fine-tuning as mentioned in the previous section.

Moreover, QLoRA introduces a technique called paged optimizers which is achieved by using NVIDIA unified memory. The intuition behind this is in occasions such as gradient check-pointing, the GPU might go out of memory, at which time paged memory⁴ allocated in GPU for optimizer states is transferred to central processing unit(CPU) random access memory (RAM). During weight updating the optimizer state is re-allocated to the GPU memory from CPU memory.

Through these means, QLoRA claims to achieve significant efficiency in fine-tuning language models where, the GPU requirement for fine-tuning a 65B model is made at less than 48GB as opposed to more than 780GB in a full fine-tune, enabling usage

⁴"page" is a fixed length block of virtual memory used by the operating system for memory management [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Page_\(computer_memory\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Page_(computer_memory))

of consumer hardware for LLM fine-tuning and cutting the time needed for fine-tune iterations significantly.

2.5. Intent Based Automation Using LLM

More recently due to the success of LLMs and their ability in fine-tuning for downstream tasks, a wide use of LLMs for automating various tasks can be observed. LLM-integrated tasks span from implementing co-pilots to fully automated solutions.

Most solutions follow a similar structure where a third party gives an intent or instruction to the LLM. The intent contains the necessary information for the LLM to produce the intended output. Mostly the intent is generated by a human or in some cases by the program itself.

In [34], the authors work on solving math problems using LLM where linguistic math problems are given as input for the LLM to solve. Here, the intent is the given math problem where output from the LLM should be the solution to the given math problem. ToolLLM [35] proposes a solution to automate the consumption of real-world APIs based on human prompts.

Automatic code generation is another area where intent-based automation is utilized. Verigen [11] uses LLM for Verilog code generation where an LLM is fine-tuned on Verilog-based text corpus. Here, code generation is achieved by giving instructions and a partial code as input to the LLM to produce the intended output code. A similar approach is followed by [10] for code generation for Golang compiler testing.

Another aspect of intent-based automation is in automating IT infrastructure management. AppleSeed [36] is one such solution where infrastructure management is automated for user prompts based on few-shot learning [37] using LLM. It is important to note that the authors are not fine-tuning a model, rather generalization ability of chatGPT is used for the purpose. Another example of infrastructure management using LLM is [38], where the authors utilize the code generation ability of LLMs to repair the code of ansible scripts written for edge cloud infrastructure management.

In conclusion, intent-based automation of complex tasks using LLMs is proposed vastly in the research community in a wide range of subjects. However, the automation of FL tasks using user intents is yet to be realized. In the later part of our work, we propose a solution to fine-tune an LLM for the downstream task of automating FL based on the user's intents.

3. SYSTEM DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

This section explains how the system is planned and designed, as well as the methods we use during the development. As discussed in previous sections our goal is to implement a web application to make FL accessible for everyone without dealing with the intricacies such as network programming to implement a communication architecture. To that end, we develop a new web application with an inbuilt communication architecture to handle FL tasks. Through that we eliminate the need for programming an FL solution from scratch, rather FL tasks are carried out using the developed web application.

Our work is mainly divided into two phases.

- In phase 1, we develop a standard web solution to orchestrate FL tasks easily.
- in phase 2, we fine-tune and integrate an LLM to further automate the developed solution.

Figure 5. Overview of FL web application solution.

3.1. Standard Web Application

The proposed solution comprises three key elements, as illustrated in Figure 5. The front-end user interface is designed to enable end users to input essential parameters required for executing an FL task. The server (PS) functions as the central coordinator, responsible for tasks such as aggregating parameters, scheduling clients, and managing database services. Additionally, individual clients run separate code locally for training, with each client capable of operating on various hardware setups, provided they possess sufficient computational resources for local training and a communication interface for interacting with the server.

The front-end web user interface is developed as a React⁵ application where Redux⁶ is used for managing the state of the front-end data. We use a web form in the front-end to get the necessary information to carry out a FL task. Comprehensive information

⁵React is an open-source front-end javascript library <https://react.dev/>

⁶Redux is a javascript library built for managing application state <https://redux.js.org/>

about the most important fields in the web form to be filled by the end user is explained using Table 1.

Table 1. Fields used in the web form and their description.

Field Name	Field Type	Description
General Information		
Task Name	Text	Unique identifier for each new FL task - data saved under this name in DB.
Host IP	Text	IP address of the PS.
Client list	Text	IP addresses of all the participating clients.
Algorithm type	Text	Selectable from below algorithms, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Classification • Regression
FL Specific Information		
Local minibatch size	Integer	Minibatch size for training the model locally.
Number of local epochs	Integer	Local iterations the local client should run.
Learning rate	Decimal	Learning rate for the optimizer used for training.
Scheduler Type	Text	Selectable from below scheduling methods <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random • Round Robin • Latency Proportional • Full

Client Fraction	Decimal	Fraction of clients out of all the clients participating in a single round of communications. A number ≤ 1 and > 0 .
Local Test Minibatch size	Integer	Minibatch size used for testing at end of each communication round.
Number of communication rounds	Integer	Total number of rounds the model is communicated between PS and the clients for aggregation.
Model Information		
Model File	File	A python file with neural network model architecture required for training, written in Pytorch
Optimization Parameters		
Optimizer	Text	Selectable from a list of Pytorch optimizers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adam • SGD • ...
Loss	Text	Selectable from a list of Loss functions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cross Entropy Loss • MSE Loss • ...
Compress	Text	Selectable from a list of compression techniques <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quantize • Topk • Random • No (no compression)

Data Information		
Data type	Text	Selectable from list of data types <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Image • Text • Regression
Train Folder	Text	Folder where training data is located in Clients.
Test Folder	Text	Folder where test data is located in the Server
Normalize	Text	Select from Yes/No to whether normalize the data. Should provide mean and std if Yes.

The user has to submit the required task information via the web form, after which the data is converted to Javascript object notation (JSON) format and transmitted to the PS to initiate the FL task.

Figure 6. HTTP Connection vs WebSockets Connection.

Websockets serve as the communication protocol for all interactions between the front-end and PS and between the PS and the clients. Websockets is a full duplex communication protocol built on top of transmission control protocol (TCP), which facilitates real-time data transfer between two communicating devices. The communication flow of websockets is depicted in Figure 6, and the choice of adopting Websockets for our use case is primarily due to,

- **Bi-Directional Data Transfer:** Websockets enable bi-directional communication between the server and the client. Since in an FL setting,

model weights must be communicated between the server and client and vice versa, this bi-directional communication enables efficient synchronization of model updates.

- **Real Time Communication:** Websockets facilitate real-time communication by maintaining a persistent connection between the client and the server. Unlike traditional hypertext transfer protocol (HTTP), which requires establishing a new connection for each request, websockets leverage an established connection, eliminating the overhead associated with connection setup. This real-time communication is advantageous for FL, where rapid exchange of model updates is crucial for collaborative learning.
- **Long-lived Connection:** Websockets connection is long-lived, meaning the connection will exist until a client deliberately closes the connection or the connection is inactive for a longer period. This allows in our use case where connections between the user interface, PS, and clients must be kept alive until respective FL tasks are carried out, which could be minutes or hours in duration.

Figure 7. Communication process between front-end, server and clients.

3.2. Fed Avg Algorithm Implementation

As mentioned in the previous section, we implement the *FedAVG* algorithm in a distributed manner where a user can initiate a *FedAVG* task by selecting required parameters from the user interface, appropriately according to the Table 1. Furthermore, we make a couple of changes to the algorithm 1 where,

1. We implement model compression schemes for efficient communication of model weights between the client and the PS. The user can select if the locally trained model by the client should be compressed using any compression schemes mentioned in Table 1 before transferring the model weights back to the PS.
2. We implement several scheduling mechanisms to select which clients are chosen for each round of communication. Any scheduler mentioned in 1 can be chosen by the user when starting an FL task.
 - **Random** option selects clients randomly according to a given client fraction. For example, if the client fraction is 0.5 and the total number of clients is 4, at the beginning of each communication round, 2 clients are selected randomly from the pool of 4 clients.
 - **Round Robin** option selects clients in a round-robin fashion. For example, if the pool of clients is $\{Client A, Client B, Client C, Client D\}$ and the client fraction is 0.5, the sequence of selecting clients for each communication round is, $\{Client A, Client B\}$, $\{Client B, Client C\}$, $\{Client C, Client D\}$, $\{Client D, Client A\}$, and so on.
 - **Latency-proportional** option selects the clients with the lowest latency averaged over a k communication rounds. For instance, if $k = 3$ the client fraction is 0.5, and 4 clients participate in training, 2 clients out of 4 will be selected according to their latency averaged over the latest 3 communication rounds.
 - **Full** option selects all the clients during each communication round. hence the client fraction is always 1 in this scenario.

With these additions in mind, we adapt the implementation of the *FedAVG* as in algorithm 2 for our web application solution. In the provided algorithm, *Compress* and *DeCompress* are functions implemented in the client program and the server program respectively for each compression scheme described earlier.

Algorithm 2. Adapted FedAvg Algorithm.

Inputs : K - number of clients, η - learning rate, C - Client fraction, E - Number of local epochs, B - local minibatch size

Server Executes :

```

initialize  $w_0$ 
for each round  $t = 1, 2, \dots$  do
   $m \leftarrow \max(C \cdot K, 1)$ 
   $S_t \leftarrow$  (set of  $m$  clients according to scheduling mechanism selected)
  for each client  $k \in S_t$  in parallel do
     $w_i \leftarrow \text{ClientUpdate}(k, w_i)$ 
    if  $\text{compress} = \text{True}$  then
       $w_{t+1}^k \leftarrow \text{DeCompress}(w_i)$ 
    else
       $w_{t+1}^k \leftarrow w_i$ 
    end
  end
   $m_t \leftarrow \sum_{k \in S_t} n_k$ 
   $w_{t+1} \leftarrow \sum_{k \in S_t} \frac{n_k}{m_t} w_{t+1}^k$ 
end

```

Client Update(k, w): *Update run on client k*

```

 $\mathcal{B} \leftarrow$  (split  $\mathcal{P}_k$  into batches of size  $B$ )
for each local epoch  $i$  from 1 to  $E$  do
  for batch  $b \in \mathcal{B}$  do
     $w \leftarrow w - \eta \Delta l(w; b)$ 
  end
end
if  $\text{compress} = \text{True}$  then
   $w_n \leftarrow \text{Compress}(w)$ 
else
   $w_n \leftarrow w$ 
end
return  $w_n$  to server.

```

The implementation of the adapted algorithm leverages websockets for communication, where the 8 high-level stages illustrated in Figure 7 is described below.

1. The first step in starting the FL communication pipeline is the user has to fill out the relevant web form and submit the FL request. A websockets request is sent to the PS where the payload in the request is in JSON format. At this point, a websockets connection between the PS and the front-end web application is made and the connection is kept alive until the end of all the communication rounds. This is required since all the intermediate communication round results are communicated to the front-end to update a dashboard to show the training metrics such as accuracy, loss, etc in real-time.

2. Once the request is received at the PS, the task of the server is to communicate the request to a list of clients. The list of clients for each communication round will be selected based on the client fraction and scheduling mechanism. At this point, a websockets connection will be made asynchronously by the PS with each client participating in a particular communication round. The global model along with the required parameters for model training is communicated to all the clients.
3. As the third step, the received global model is trained locally by each client on the dataset specified for a given number of local epochs, incorporating the received parameters such as mini-batch size, optimizer to use, loss function, etc.
4. Once the client trains the local model, each client communicates the trained model weights back to the PS as the fourth step. The server receives these model weights asynchronously whenever a client finishes the training task. Once the results from all the participating clients are transferred, websockets connections between the PS and each respective client will be closed.
5. In this next step, the PS aggregates the received local models from all the participating clients to update the global model.
6. Once the global model is updated, test results for the updated model are calculated using the test dataset located on the PS. At this point, training results, test results, and model parameters are saved into a database for later comparisons.
7. Next all the results including training and test metrics for the current communication round are sent back to the front-end via the existing websockets connection.
8. Finally, the web application dashboard is updated whenever a result is received from the PS, thus updating in real time in sync with the communication rounds. The results such as test accuracy, training loss, training accuracy, time taken for each communication round, etc. can be plotted as shown in Figure 8 where the user can select which plots must be plotted during the initial submission at the first step.

The above 2-8 steps are carried out iteratively until all the communication rounds the user requested are completed, while the websockets connection between the front-end and PS is kept alive until the completion.

Figure 8. Dashboard of the web interface to show the requested plots and training information.

3.3. Web Application with LLM Support

As discussed in a previous section, with the advent of LLMs, automating tasks based on natural language prompts has been widely adopted in the AI community. In this section, emphasis is given to integrating an LLM for automating the FL process based on user prompts.

Figure 9. Overview of LLM integration with FL web application.

An overview of the proposed solution is illustrated in Figure 9, where the web application user interface is accustomed for a user to input details about the FL task in natural language rather than selecting parameters in a web form. This prompt is sent to the PS to process where the the server will perform the FL process according to the

prompt provided by the user. To accommodate that, we fine-tune an LLM model on a new dataset customized for our use case.

3.3.1. LLM Finetuning

The downstream task in our proposed solution is carrying out an FL task based on the user prompt provided. Thus, the LLM needs to be fine-tuned so that the output from the LLM should be compatible with the PS. In our previous case with the standard web application, the payload in the request from the user contained a JSON, which carries information required for the FL task such as model parameters, optimizer parameters, etc. Hence, it is natural to use the same structure of the JSON as output from the LLM to make the new solution compatible with the previously developed one.

Figure 10. Fine-tuning process of LLM to be compatible with PS.

As depicted in Figure 10, to fine-tune the LLM, we create a dataset with <INTENT, TARGET> pairs where INTENT is the user prompt provided by the user while the TARGET is the intended JSON output by the LLM for the provided intent.

Dataset for fine-tuning LLM

We create a new dataset with 1504 data points with <INTENT, TARGET> pairs for fine-tuning the LLM. The dataset is created while considering a wider range of possible variations that could occur in the user intent. For example, the user intent can be as simple as follows,

Prompt1: *Perform a Federated learning task with MNIST dataset*

where only the dataset is specified neglecting all other parameters that could occur in the intent. On the other hand, it can take a more complex form where more parameters are specified as in the below prompt.

Prompt2: *Create a Federate learning task with MNIST dataset. Run for a total of 20 communication rounds and run for 12 local epochs. Use SGD as the optimizer with a learning rate of 0.004. Use a mini-batch size of 32 for training. Client fraction should be 0.7.*

The target JSON should be accustomed according to the provided intent. One caveat here is when the prompt becomes simple, values to be used in the JSON for the unspecified parameters become unclear. To overcome this, we use some default values for the parameters whenever the parameter is not specified in the prompt, as specified in Table 2. Some of the default values like learning rate are derived experimentally by running for common datasets used in our work such as MNIST and CIFAR-10.

Table 2. Default values to be used for parameters when unspecified in the prompt.

Key	Value
minibatch	16
algo	Classification
epoch	5
lr	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adam - 0.0001 • SGD - 0.001 • AdaGrad - 0.004 • RMSProp - 0.0004
scheduler	full (random if clientFraction < 1)
clientFraction	1
minibatchtest	32
comRounds	10
optimizer	Adam
loss	CrossEntropyLoss
compress	No

In that regard, the output for the **Prompt1** is as follows where the default values are used as per the provided table. Only the dataset is derived from the intent as MNIST, while all other values are kept default.

Target1:

```
{ "algo": "Classification",
  "minibatch": "16",
  "epoch": "5",
  "lr": "0.0001",
  "scheduler": "full",
  "clientFraction": "1",
  "minibatchtest": "32",
  "comRounds": "10",
  "optimizer": "Adam",
```

```
"loss": "CrossEntropyLoss",
"compress": "No",
"dataset": "MNIST"}
```

On the other hand target output for **Prompt2** is as follows where all the specified values are used to override the default values while unspecified values are kept default.

Target1:

```
{"algo": "Classification",
"minibatch": "32",
"epoch": "12",
"lr": "0.004",
"scheduler": "random",
"clientFraction": "0.7",
"minibatchtest": "32",
"comRounds": "20",
"optimizer": "SGD",
"loss": "CrossEntropyLoss",
"compress": "No",
"dataset": "MNIST"}
```

For example, since a client fraction is given in the prompt, a scheduler other than `full` should be used. The default value for the scheduler whenever a client fraction is specified is set to `random`, in the dataset.

As illustrated in Figure 11, all the possible variations for the scheduler and several variations of optimizer choices are included in the dataset. As observed in the plots, the number of instances containing default values is higher. This is due to the higher number of data points not specifying the relevant parameter in the intent. For example, it is natural for a user to input only the `clientFraction`, but not the `scheduler`, where in such cases the default value is used.

Figure 11. Scheduler and optimizer variations across the dataset.

One other aspect considered when developing the dataset is possible variation in phrasing the user intent. For example, when the `clientFraction` needs to be specified in the intent, it can be phrased in several ways as follows.

Prompt: *Create a federated learning task with MNIST dataset with a client fraction of 0.7.*

Prompt: *Perform a federated learning task with MNIST dataset with involving 70% of the total clients.*

Prompt: *Execute a federated learning task with MNIST dataset with involving 7/10 of the total clients.*

Prompt: *Start a federated learning task with MNIST dataset by omitting 30% of total clients in each communication round.*

The output JSON of all above prompts should be the same and the dataset is created by including similar variations throughout the dataset for other parameters as well. Apart from that, several other actions are taken to induce variation to the dataset such as paraphrasing, differing complexity of the sentence structure, and differing the order of parameters provided in the intent.

To get good results when fine-tuning an LLM, structuring the prompt is very important. Apart from the user intent and the target response, a system instruction is added to the input prompt. System instruction can provide contextual guidance to the model, informing it about the task at hand or the desired behavior. This helps the model understand the specific requirements of the fine-tuning task and adjust its predictions accordingly. In our case, the system prompt is used as below to communicate the role of the LLM succinctly.

System Prompt: *Your task is to provide a json given a instruction by the user for a federated learning task. The output should be in JSON format. Keys for JSON are algo - Classification/Regression, minibatch - size of minibatch (16), epoch- number of epochs(5), lr - learning rate, scheduler - full/random/round_robin/latency_proportional(full), clientFraction- fraction of clients involved in federated learning (1), comRounds- number of communication rounds in federated learning(10), optimizer-pytorch optimizer(Adam), loss(CrossEntropyLoss), compress- No/quantize(No), dtype-img(img),dataset-dataset used for training. Default values for each key are given inside the bracket.Separated by / are possible values for the relevant key. Your task is to create a JSON with the above keys and extract possible values from a given human prompt as values for the JSON. Respond only the JSON.*

A detailed description of each parameter of the output JSON is given by the System Prompt for helping to predict the output accurately. The System prompt is kept static throughout all the data points since we are fine-tuning for a single downstream task and the intended output structure is the same for all the user intents. Finally, each data-point is customized using the System Prompt, Intent, and Target as mentioned below before feeding into the fine-tuning pipeline⁷.

⁷Finalized dataset is hosted in huggingface https://huggingface.co/datasets/cmarvolo/auto_fl

Instruction: <SYSTEM PROMPT> ### Input: <INTENT> ###
 Response: <TARGET>

Fine-tuning process

The dataset described in the previous section is used to fine-tune a Mistral-7B[25] model. The fine-tuning process is carried out for two epochs through the dataset using the QLoRA method. Hence, the model is loaded in 4-bit precision for fine-tuning where at the end of the training, the LoRA module is merged with the base model by upscaling the trained LoRA to 8-bit precision⁸.

We use Adamw_8bit, an 8-bit precision variation of adamW[39] optimizer, as the optimizer with a learning rate of 2×10^{-4} for fine-tuning. A single A100 GPU provided by Google Colab is used for fine-tuning where Unsloth [40] library is used for efficient fine-tuning. Unsloth is an open-source library that provides Python API for faster fine-tuning of LLMs.

3.3.2. LLM Integration to Web Application

Once an open-source LLM model is fine-tuned for our task of automating FL for user prompts, the model must be integrated into the existing solution. An overview of the system design for the initial integration of LLM into the existing solution is depicted in Figure 12.

Figure 12. System design for initial integration of LLM to the existing solution.

We implement a separate server to host the LLM model where a Representational State Transfer (REST) API endpoint is created to consume the LLM service. The

⁸Fine-tuned LoRA adapter is hosted in huggingface <https://huggingface.co/cmavolo/mistral-7b-fed-auto-lora>

REST endpoint named `/get_config` is developed using the Python FLASK library to return the JSON configuration matching the user intent.

We convert the fine-tuned LLM model to GGUF format before hosting in the LLM Server, where GGUF is a binary file format used for storing LLM models for inference where loading and saving models are made faster. A Python binding ⁹ for llama.cpp ¹⁰ is used for serving the model inside the provided REST endpoint.

As depicted in the diagram, the procedure followed in the proposed architecture is as follows,

1. An intent is submitted by the user using the front-end web interface describing the nature of the FL task to be carried out.
2. The PS, receives the request and forwards the received intent to the LLM server.
3. LLM server receives the request with intent as the payload from the PS. The LLM server processes the received intent using the fine-tuned model to output the target JSON for the received intent. The generated output JSON is responded to the PS.
4. The PS carries out the general FL procedure with the received JSON configuration while coordinating with the clients. In this case, the model architecture for training should be stored in client devices beforehand since the model architecture for training is not uploaded.
5. During the FL training process, the results are communicated with the front-end web interface as in earlier cases with the Standard web application.

One major drawback of the solution proposed above is the inability to select a global model architecture specific to the dataset in the FL process. Unlike the standard web application solution, where there was the option of uploading the model architecture file used for the training, it is not feasible in this case since intent is provided in natural language, and providing a model architecture in natural language is a complex and tedious task. Accordingly, we employ another approach where the reasoning power of GPT models is utilized in proposing a global model for carrying out a particular FL task.

Below is a prompt provided for OpenAI ChatGPT API ¹¹ to suggest neural network architecture for a couple of intended tasks.

Prompt: *Suggest two different Pytorch CNN model architectures for the following two tasks. And explain the reason for choosing the particular architecture.*

1. *An image classification task with 28x28 size. There are altogether 1000 images in the dataset and the classification is done for 5 labeled classes.*

⁹Python binding for llama.cpp <https://github.com/abetlen/llama-cpp-python>

¹⁰llama.cpp library <https://github.com/ggerganov/llama.cpp>

¹¹ChatGPT link - <https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt>

2. Another image classification task where the image size is 32x32 and has 100000 images, and 10 labeled classes.

As evident from the above prompt, the first task is an image classification task where the number of data points is lower while the other task is also a classification task with a significantly higher number of data points. Also, the input dimension and the number of classification classes differ between the two tasks.

```
python
import torch
import torch.nn as nn

class LeNet5(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, num_classes=0):
        super(LeNet5, self).__init__()
        self.conv1 = nn.Conv2d(1, 6, kernel_size=5, stride=1, padding=2)
        self.relu1 = nn.ReLU()
        self.pool1 = nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2)
        self.conv2 = nn.Conv2d(6, 16, kernel_size=5, stride=1, padding=0)
        self.relu2 = nn.ReLU()
        self.pool2 = nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2)
        self.flatten = nn.Flatten()
        self.fc1 = nn.Linear(16 * 5 * 5 * 2, 120)
        self.relu3 = nn.ReLU()
        self.fc2 = nn.Linear(120, 84)
        self.relu4 = nn.ReLU()
        self.fc3 = nn.Linear(84, num_classes)

    def forward(self, x):
        x = self.pool1(self.relu1(self.conv1(x)))
        x = self.pool2(self.relu2(self.conv2(x)))
        x = self.flatten(x)
        x = self.relu3(self.fc1(x))
        x = self.relu4(self.fc2(x))
        x = self.fc3(x)
        return x
```

LeNet-5 Architecture

```
python
import torch
import torch.nn as nn

class VGG16(nn.Module):
    def __init__(self, num_classes=0):
        super(VGG16, self).__init__()
        self.features = nn.Sequential(
            nn.Conv2d(3, 64, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.Conv2d(64, 64, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2),
            nn.Conv2d(64, 128, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.Conv2d(128, 128, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2),
            nn.Conv2d(128, 256, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.Conv2d(256, 256, kernel_size=3, padding=1),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.MaxPool2d(kernel_size=2, stride=2),
        )
        self.classifier = nn.Sequential(
            nn.Linear(256 * 5 * 5 * 2, 4096),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.Linear(4096, 4096),
            nn.ReLU(inplace=True),
            nn.Linear(4096, num_classes),
        )

    def forward(self, x):
        x = self.features(x)
        x = x.view(x.size()[0], -1)
        x = self.classifier(x)
        return x
```

VGG16 architecture

Figure 13. Model architectures proposed by ChatGPT for the provided prompt: LeNet-5 (task 1) & VGG16 (task2).

The model architectures suggested for the above two tasks in the prompt are shown in Figure 13 and the reasoning provided by ChatGPT API is as follows.

Reasoning for Model1:

- LeNet-5 is a classic architecture and is suitable for small image sizes.
- The dataset being small (1000 images) makes a simpler model like LeNet-5 appropriate to prevent overfitting.
- The number of parameters is relatively small, making it efficient for a small dataset.

Reasoning for Model2:

- VGG16 is a deeper architecture that has shown good performance on various image classification tasks.
- The dataset being larger (100,000 images) allows for training a more complex model like VGG16 without overfitting.

- The increased depth allows the model to learn more complex features from the larger dataset.

The reasoning above suggests that ChatGPT has the capability to suggest a neural network architecture for a given training task based on input dimensions, number data points, and labels. We intend to leverage this capability to propose a model architecture for FL tasks.

Since data is a commodity of the clients in the FL process, responsibility of providing the details of the dataset is given to the clients. A configuration file along with the dataset should be kept in the data folder, which holds information such as dimension, number of data points, task, and number of labels as depicted in Figure 14.

Using this provided configuration file a new prompt is created to query ChatGPT for a model architecture. Following is a sample prompt for a classification task where the underlined values are derived from the configuration file provided.

User_Prompt: *Create a model architecture for the following task. Task is a Classification task with 12 labels. image size is 32x32 and is 1 channel and have 5000 datapoints altogether. Considering above information create a neural network architecture which could achieve good accuracy*

Like in the previous case, a preceding system prompt is added to the above prompt to advise the LLM about the required output.

System_Prompt: *You are an AI that strictly conforms to responses in Python. Your responses consist of valid python syntax, with no other comments, explanations, reasoning, or dialogue not consisting of valid Python. Your task is to output pytorch Model code according to the given user prompt Only include pytorch imports, init function and the forward pass function. Do not include code for initializing the model*

The final prompt is structured as a JSON as represented below to be compatible with the ChatGPT API. The gpt-3.5-turbo is used as the model for inference.

```
{ "role": "system", content:<System_prompt>,
  "role": "user", content:<User_prompt> }
```

A separate endpoint named /get_model_architecture is hosted in the LLM Server where the PS sends the dataset configuration to this endpoint and a request to the ChatGPT API is sent by the LLM server with the prompt structured as mentioned above.

As portrayed in Figure 14, a summary of the entire application process is as follows.

1. User sends intent in natural language to the PS.
2. PS receives the provided intent and forwards the intent to the endpoint /get_config of the LLM server.
3. LLM server processes the intent using the LLM model and returns the output as a JSON to the PS.

Figure 14. Finalized system architecture with LLM support.

4. PS queries a client selected randomly for the dataset configuration file including properties of the dataset.
5. Client responds to the PS with the dataset configuration file stored in the particular dataset folder.
6. PS forwards the dataset configuration to the LLM server.
7. LLM server overrides the default prompt structure with the information received in the dataset configuration file. This newly created prompt is forwarded to ChatGPT to receive the model architecture. The received model architecture is responded back to the PS.
8. PS receives the model architecture for the FL task from the LLM server and the FL process is carried out with the received model architecture set as the global model architecture.
9. Intermediate results are responded back to the web interface.

4. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this chapter, we present the results of the evaluation of the fine-tuned LLM, and experimental results carried out using the standard web application and the LLM integrated web application.

4.1. LLM Fine Tuning Results

To evaluate the performance of the fine-tuned language model, we create a new test dataset comprising 355 instances similar to the fine-tuned dataset. The dataset is designed to span from simpler prompts with minimal specified parameters to complex prompts with many parameters included, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation spectrum. Additionally, for categorical parameters such as optimizers, new values were added to test the generalization capability of the LLM as evident from Figure 15 where Adadelta and SparseAdam were not used as optimizers in the intents in fine-tune dataset. Similarly, values for the *dataset* key were also given unseen values with random dataset names to evaluate the generalizability.

Figure 15. Optimizer variations in the intents in the test dataset.

The evaluation accuracy of the test dataset holds at 99.4% where only for two data points an incorrect output is predicted. Detailed information about mismatched results is given below.

Prompt: *Use the MNIST dataset for training a federated learning model with just 0.001% of clients. Implement a random scheduling approach and apply any compression technique during the training. Carry out the training with the Adam optimization method.*

Output:

```
{
  "algo": "Classification",
  "minibatch": "16",
  "epoch": "5",
  "lr": "0.0001",
  "scheduler": "random",
  "clientFraction": "0.000001",
  "minibatchtest": "32",
  "comRounds": "10",
  "optimizer": "Adam",
  "loss": "CrossEntropyLoss",
  "compress": "quantize",
  "compress_bits": 8,
  "dtype": "img",
  "dataset": "MNIST"
}
```

The first prompt that failed to provide a correct output is depicted above where the LLM fails to correctly produce the client fraction where the clientFraction is produced as 0.000001 instead of the correct value 0.00001. It is evident that LLM fails to do proper division in this instance.

Prompt: *Design an FL assignment with COCO dataset where each of the 50 clients has particular duties. Employ the Adam optimizer and apply weight quantization.*

Output:

```
{
  "algo": "Classification",
  "minibatch": "16",
  "epoch": "5",
  "lr": "0.0001",
  "scheduler": "full",
  "clientFraction": "0.5",
  "minibatchtest": "32",
  "comRounds": "10",
  "optimizer": "Adam",
  "loss": "CrossEntropyLoss",
  "compress": "quantize",
  "compress_bits": 8,
  "dtype": "img",
  "dataset": "COCO"
}
```

As underlined in the above JSON, the LLM fails again to properly predict the clientFraction where the correct number should be 1, but the predicted value is 0.5. This could be attributed to the hallucination effect of LLM where the "50 clients" phrase in the prompt could be mistaken as a percentage by the LLM.

However, due to the accurate prediction of all other 353 intents in the test set with comparable complexity, we assert that the fine-tuned LLM in its present state is suitable for integration with the web application in our use case.

4.2. Federated Learning Simulation through Web App Results

Several simulations are carried out using the standard FL web application and the LLM-integrated solution to evaluate the results using both solutions. The outcomes obtained from the standard FL application are denoted as `WebFed`, whereas those from the LLM-integrated solution are referred to as `LLMFed` for clarity in the presentation of results.

For both forms of simulations, three Raspberry Pi modules are used as clients and both the PS and the LLM server are run on a single Laptop with an i7-9750H CPU, 24GB RAM, and a NVIDIA GeForce 1660Ti GPU with 6GB dedicated memory. All the devices are connected to a single local network for wireless communication between the devices.

MNIST and CIFAR-10 datasets are used for all the simulations where the dataset is partitioned into four distinct sets and equally distributed among three clients and the server. The simulations are run for several cases by differing the parameters required for the FL task.

Case 1: An FL task is initialized using `WebFed` with a client fraction = 0.7, local minibatch size = 4 and local number of epochs = 1, communication rounds = 50, optimizer = Adam, learning rate = 0.0001. The global model architecture in Figure 16 is submitted as a Python file.

Similarly, for the `LLMFed` process, the following prompt is given to capture the same parameters as above.

Prompt: *Create a federated learning task using the MNIST dataset. Use Adam as the optimizer with a learning rate of 0.0001. Minibatch size should be set to 4 while the number of local epochs should be 1. Run for total of 50 communication rounds. Use a client fraction of 0.7 for training.*

The model suggested by the LLM shown in Figure 16 is chosen automatically as the global model architecture. As seen from the Figure the model architectures are almost identical except for the number of parameters differing slightly.

The plots in Figure 17 illustrate that `WebFed` outperforms in terms of both test accuracy and test loss. Nonetheless, the variance is slight, as both models manage to attain an accuracy exceeding 98% for Case 1. The total bytes transferred and the time elapsed for the operation is low on the `LLMFed` as observed in the plots in the same Figure. This is because the model `LLMFed` has suggested having fewer parameters than the model manually uploaded through the Web. However, a closer look at the elapsed time plot we can see that, the time taken by the `LLMFed` for the first communication round aligns with the time taken by `WebFed`, while subsequent times taken is very less in comparison. This is because of the added overhead by `LLMFed` in the first communication round for inferences done by the LLM.

Figure 16. Global model architecture submitted as a file in the web form of the standard web application for WebFed (Top) and the global model suggested by the LLM for LLMFed (Bottom) for case1.

Figure 17. Test accuracy, test loss, elapsed time, total bytes transferred plots for WebFed and LLMFed for case 1.

Case 2: For the next scenario, an FL task is carried out using the CIFAR-10 dataset. In this scenario, data is distributed among 3 clients and the PS with 16000 data points for each client and server. As depicted in Figure 18, a new model architecture is created by adjusting the dimensions of the previous `WebFed` model to accommodate the new dataset. The FL task is carried out using a client fraction of 0.7 with random scheduling for 100 communication rounds. Minibatch size = 8, number of local epochs = 2, learning rate = 0.001 with Adam optimizer is used as the parameters for training. Similar to the previous case, the prompt below captures all the parameters mentioned here.

Prompt: *Perform a federated learning job using the cfar10 dataset. Use Adam as the optimizer with a learning rate of 0.001. Run for a total of 100 communication rounds with 2 local rounds. Use random scheduling for a client fraction of 0.7. Local minibatch size for training should be used as 8.*

Figure 18. Global model architecture submitted as a file in the web form of the standard web application for `WebFed` (Top) and the global model suggested by the LLM for `LLMFed` (Bottom) for case2.

Comparing the model architectures in Figure 18 for `WebFed` and `LLMFed`, we observe that, for case2, LLM suggests a model architecture with an additional layer of Conv2D and a MaxPool2D layer. However, despite the additional layer number of parameters is lower in `LLMFed`, due to differing layer dimensions.

Observing the plots in Figure 19, it is evident that the model proposed by `LLMFed`, outperforms in test accuracy and test loss compared to the model manually crafted for `WebFed`. Also, the elapsed time and bytes transferred in `LLMFed` are lower due to the lesser number of parameters in the suggested model.

Figure 19. Test accuracy, test loss, elapsed time, total bytes transferred plots for WebFed and LLMFed for Case 2.

Case 3: In this case we simulate WebFed scenario in Case 1 to compare compression schemes implemented in the solution. The same model and hyperparameters as Case 1 are utilized while 8-bit quantization, top 50%, and random 50% compression schemes are simulated. The simulation is run for 5 rounds for each scenario above and averaged results are plotted in Figure 20.

When considering test accuracy and test loss for this Case we observe that results obtained with WebFed with compression enabled achieve comparable results as WebFed without compression schemes. Moreover, analyzing the total elapsed times, much variations are not observed, since compression is done after the training and significant time is taken for the training stage rather than the weight communication stage. However, a considerable variation can be observed in the total bytes transferred plot since model sizes are significantly reduced during the compression scheme. Hence, the major advantage of enabling compression schemes is the reduction of model size for efficient communication of model weights between the client and PS where communication bottlenecks can be alleviated.

Figure 20. Test accuracy, Test loss, Elapsed time, Total bytes transferred plots for WebFed for Case 3.

4.3. Discussion

The objective of this thesis is to implement a web-based solution to easily orchestrate FL tasks. Accordingly, a standard web application, WebFed and an LLM integrated solution, LLMFed are developed and evaluated in the previous section.

The developed solution provides the flexibility of carrying out FL tasks easily with customized parameters according to the task using a dataset of choice. The user of the system just needs to store the dataset for training in the client device and submit the necessary parameters and a compatible model architecture through the provided web interface to perform the FL task. Creating the communication architecture and other intricacies in developing an FL solution from scratch is eliminated in the provided solution.

The results carried out using common datasets in FL literature are comparable with previous research [1], indicating the reliability of results obtained by our solution. Furthermore, other secondary FL functionalities such as compression schemes and scheduling mechanisms are implemented in the solution. From the results, it is evident that through enabling compression schemes a good test accuracy is achieved while reducing the number of bytes transferred, which helps in alleviating bottlenecks in communication.

As mentioned in the previous section, the simulations are carried out by using Raspberry Pi modules as clients. This indicates the adaptability of the provided solutions. Given enough computing power and a wireless communication interface any device can be used as a client, by just running the client program on the device. This enables using heterogeneous devices as clients in the FL task.

Furthermore, LLMFed extension to the standard WebFed solution further automates the FL process for user intents. Results obtained in the previous section indicate that automated results achieve good accuracy comparable to the standard solution while in some cases giving better results. However, there remains uncertainty with the LLMFed solution, as the model architecture used in this setting is generated by the GPT in a somewhat arbitrary manner. Although the results achieved in the tested scenarios are promising, it is not guaranteed that similar outcomes would be obtained for other datasets. Hence, experimenting with more complex datasets and improving upon the automated solution is kept as future work.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

In summary, this thesis introduces a web-based solution for orchestrating FL tasks, designed to be accessible to researchers without extensive programming knowledge. Complex communications for seamless support for FL tasks are implemented using an efficient websockets architecture. Furthermore, the integration of intent-based automation, achieved through fine-tuning an LLM, further enhances user accessibility by allowing FL processes to be automated via natural language prompts. Experimental results suggest that the automated approach sometimes outperforms handcrafted models. Yet manual optimization of neural network architectures and hyperparameters remains a viable strategy for achieving superior performance, particularly for complex datasets beyond the scope of standard benchmarks like MNIST and CIFAR-10. Hence, future research will explore automating the search for optimal architectures through neural architecture search and hyperparameter optimization as an extension to the work carried out during this thesis.

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7. APPENDICES

Appendix 1 Screenshots of the web application used to orchestrate FL tasks.

The general web form is used to fill in information such as task name, server and client IP addresses, and type of FL task.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "General Information". On the left is a dark sidebar with navigation options: "Dashboard", "New Task" (highlighted), "View Task List", and "History". The main form area contains the following fields and sections:

- Task Name:** A text input field containing "RELINEXT".
- Task Device:** A text input field containing "Analog Interpolated for Federated Learning".
- Training Dataset:** A dropdown menu with "Federated Learning_Anti-DDS" selected.
- Algorithm Type:** A dropdown menu with "Coalition" selected.
- Server IP:** A text input field containing "192.168.1.100".
- Client IP:** A list of three text input fields, each containing "192.168.1.100".
- Send File Required:** Three sections, each with a "Yes" dropdown (set to "Communication Rounds"), a "No" dropdown (set to "Yes"), and a "Yes/No" dropdown (set to "Yes").

Figure 21. General information web form

The federated learning web form takes FL parameters such as client fraction, communication rounds, etc. used for the task.

The screenshot shows a web form titled "Federated Learning". It contains the following fields:

- Local File Path:** A text input field containing "1".
- Number of Local Models:** A text input field containing "1".
- Learning Rate:** A text input field containing "0.01".
- Schedule Type:** A dropdown menu with "Random" selected.
- Client Fraction:** A text input field containing "0.1".
- Local File Path for Test:** A text input field containing "1".
- Number of Communication Rounds:** A text input field containing "10".

Figure 22. Federated learning web form

The model overview web form is used to get the model architecture and information about the model

Figure 23. Model overview web form

The model parameter web form takes the parameters for training the model such as optimizer, loss, and compression schemes.

Figure 24. Model parameter web form

The dataset parameters web form takes the information about the dataset such as data location and data normalization parameters.

Figure 25. Dataset parameter web form

The intent submission web form is for the LLMFed use case where task name, server IP address, client IPs, and intent for the FL task are taken as inputs.

The screenshot shows a web form for submitting federated learning tasks. It features a dark sidebar with navigation options: Dashboard, New Task, New Task GPT (highlighted), and History. The main form area has the following sections:

- Task Name:** A text input field containing "fl_intent_task".
- Enter the Host IP:** A text input field containing "localhost".
- Client IP:** Three input fields containing "192.168.1.31:5000", "100.75.16.123:5000", and "192.168.1.32:5002".
- + Add Client:** A button to add more client IP addresses.
- Enter description of intended Federated learning task:** A large text area containing "Perform a Federated learning task with MNIST dataset".
- Submit:** A blue button at the bottom of the form.

Figure 26. Intent submission web form

The history tab is a web interface developed to compare previously carried out tasks that are stored in the database.

Figure 27. History Tab